

Quantum Mechanics and A Breakdown of Deterministic Motion?

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Newtonian mechanics focuses on dx and dt units which tend to zero and so presents, it seems, a smoothed over or averaged type of motion. This motion in principle extends to dx and dt values which are almost zero. There is, however, a priori no reason not to expect that such a smooth averaging is at some length scale based on another kind of motion. The question is: What should that "other" kind of motion be? If it is deterministic in x and t , one may reapply the idea of this motion breaking down at yet some smaller scale. Thus it seems one should consider decoupling of x and t because one cannot follow a particle from one x point to another in time within some small length scale as this would be deterministic.

The opposite approach seems to be a probabilistic one with t and x decoupled. The external ruler and clock which exist in the Newtonian picture, however, do not disappear simply because a length scale is small. Thus having x positions based on probabilities at some length scale still uses the notion of the probability itself being smoothed over because it contains x which may take on any value. This is not necessarily a problem because the probabilistic behaviour must still appear to be Newtonian on average and so x and t based on the external clock/ruler with infinite resolution need to "appear" again. (For example, an electron has a wavelength and exhibits interference from two slits, but while moving towards the slits, distance = velocity* time with distance and time measured by an external clock. It is a mathematical generalization, however, to expect that $d=vt$ actually fully describes motion (i.e. other than on average) within a wavelength length. If it did there would be no interference pattern.

The idea of a smoothed over (or averaged motion) based on probabilistic motion also appears in the classical world, but for many particles. For example, a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with no potential has uniform density. If one considers a hypothetical box containing many molecules, it is like a Newtonian stationary object with a balance of pressure. In the case of a potential (1-D) one may consider a dx unit (with many molecules) and balance Force(x) density(x) with the difference of pressure to find the density distribution proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. These ideas are completely Newtonian, but they are smoothed over average notions. At a microscopic level molecules undergo probabilistic collisions linked to T (temperature). Thus the microscopic picture is not static - it is only the equilibrium average or big picture which is static. Even in the case of no potential, focusing on a tiny region of space smaller than the interparticle average separation and arguing that density is constant seems to be an average argument which bypasses much of the reality.

If x and t may then become probabilistic and $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant, then why should there not be stochasticity linked with E and p ? In fact we argue they are == as shown by Maxwell's solution of a photon from his electromagnetic equations. E and p (energy and momentum) are average values. Their density is given by: $\frac{1}{2}C^2(\text{Electric field dot Electric field} + \text{Magnetic field dot Magnetic field})$ and the Poynting vector for momentum. Both the Electric field and Magnetic field fluctuate as $\cos(-Et+px)$ with E and p being average values. At first this was ascribed to wave motion in a medium, but in 1905 Einstein's photoelectric arguments against energy being spread out seem to suggest a breakdown of deterministic physics

describing a wave in a medium. Instead a photon is probabilistic and has a wavefunction of Electric + i Magnetic field. (2)

A Breakdown of Deterministic Motion Rather Than One Deterministic Motion Replacing Another?

Newtonian mechanics is deterministic and uses variables x and t (time) which may take on any value. One may consider any infinitesimally small region and the motion still follows the same rules. This seems, however, like a mathematical generalization and one may argue it should break down at some length scale, although it is not clear a priori what that length should be. Classical physics already contains an example of deterministic, smooth average motion (or lack of it) based on probabilistic motion. This is found in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas which consists of molecules/particles at a temperature which undergo many random probabilistic collisions. The MB probability $\exp(-\{p^2/2m + V(x)\}/T)$ applies even though macroscopically one has Newtonian statics. For example if no potential is present, a subset box of material (with many particles) appears as a Newtonian object at rest with pressure balance. If a potential is present, $-dV/dx$ density(x) is balanced by the pressure difference using $PV = nRT$. This is a Newtonian static problem on average with T representing the stochastic part of the problem. If one were to zoom in on a tiny region of space smaller than interparticle separation, the idea of constant density (no $V(x)$) does not seem to describe physically the situation, (although on average this notion is fine).

We argue that even on the basis of the classical world there is no reason not to believe there may be an underlying behaviour, perhaps stochastic, which gives rise to a smoothed over Newtonian type picture. This begs the question: Is this underlying behaviour also deterministic i.e based on $x(t)$? If this were the case, then the argument that it should also breakdown at some smaller x , t scale should also hold. Thus we argue that a breakdown means that one does not follow x in t i.e. the two become independent. How then does one follow x ? x is measured by an external ruler (as in the Newtonian smoothed over average picture) and this ruler does not disappear because a length scale is small. It seems one must shift to a probabilistic view i.e. introduce a probability of finding a particle at x within a certain length region. This view, however, must map to the Newtonian one as in the example of uniform motion. Thus the probabilistic scheme within a certain special length should repeat itself to give a sense of uniform motion. In fact, it must be more than this. It must map to uniform motion for all x (measured by the external infinite resolution ruler). Thus one has a characteristic length with no time and an x probability distribution such that it somehow is equivalent to uniform motion (which is the opposite and does not distinguish between x points) for uniform motion.

Probabilistic x Behaviour Mapping to Newtonian Uniform Motion

We argue above that Newtonian motion is based on x and t measured by an external ruler/clock which has infinite resolution. We then suggest that at a certain length scale the notion of $x(t)$ breaks down, x and t become independent and x is represented by a probability distribution within this special length. This distribution then repeats itself (periodically) in space. The suggestion that there is a breakdown in $x(t)$ does not mean that the particle does not still

move on average as $x=vt$ ($v=\text{constant}$) for uniform motion. For example, an electron moving towards a two slit apparatus moves as $d=vt$ even though its probability distribution determines the outcome of two slit interference.

Velocity in the Newtonian picture requires two variables x and t . We argue that two variables or dimensions are then required in the probabilistic x only scenario. In other words using probability density one must describe uniform motion to the right or left. Furthermore even though there is a different probability value at each x , this must somehow map into the result that all x points are the same. Given the vector nature of the two dimensional motion representation i.e. $P(p,x) = F(p,x) + i G(p,x)$ one may suggest a constant modulus.

Furthermore given that one cannot follow the particle in time there is no notion of it moving forward or backwards as t_1 becomes t_2 . A scalar $F(p,x)$ cannot be skewed to the right or left because this does not map into all x points having the same probability in a smoothed over Newtonian picture. Thus we suggest that $F(p,x) = \text{even}$ and $G(p,x) = \text{odd}$, that they both be periodic with symmetric repeating units and have a modulus of 1. In (1) we give arguments that the form should be $\exp(ipx)$ for uniform motion.

Here we suggest that stochastic motion may give rise to the sense of uniform motion i.e. the Newtonian average. This uniform motion in turn has the mathematical semblance of existing at any x even though the probabilistic behaviour is restricted to a certain length i.e. the wavelength. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to a fixed wavelength proportional to $1/p$, yet $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ at any x i.e. in regions much smaller than the wavelength.

The Photon and Stochastic Energy and Momentum

A wave equation for the electric and magnetic fields of a photon follows from Maxwell's equations. The form $\cos(-Et+px)$, however, contains smooth values for E, t, p and x . The Poynting form (3), however, $d/dt (.5 C_1 \text{ Electric dot Electric} + .5 C_2 \text{ Magnetic dot Magnetic}) + \text{grad dot } C_3 \text{ Electric cross magnetic} = 0$, however, shows fluctuating energy and momentum densities with E and p being average values. At the time (late 1800s) it may have been thought that light was a wave in a medium and so average values (i.e. probabilities and spread out energy and momentum) were fine. With Einstein's 1905 photoelectric work, however, it became clear that energy and momentum could not be spread out in space. Thus the periodic electric and magnetic fields and their association with energy and momentum density is perhaps the beginning of a breakdown of deterministic motion.

For instance, Fermat's principle describes how light reflects and refracts and this is consistent with Newtonian conservation of the "average" momentum value in the x direction (if the flat mirror or medium interface also lies in the x direction). Even reflection from a moving mirror may be solved using Fermat's principle. Nevertheless the same light which is involved with conservation of average momentum exhibits fluctuating energy and momentum densities. This seems to show a duality i.e. a fluctuation or probabilistic view together with a smoothed over average (conservation of momentum) view at the same time. Light which reflects/refracts also exhibits diffraction and interference. If such duality may exist for the variables E and p , then given the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which treats (p,E) and (x,t) as four vectors, one may speculate that the four vector (x,t) should also have such a duality. This duality appears, we

argue, for particles with rest mass which exhibit a wavelength associated with $\exp(ipx)$ for uniform motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Newton's smooth over $x(t)$ behaviour, which mathematically holds for any x and t i.e. and dx and dt interval, no matter how small, may physically break down before this, even though the average (which loses information) still holds for all x and t . This idea may already be seen in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with constant density ($V(x)=0$). A small portion of the gas (containing many molecules) is like a Newtonian object with a balanced pressure. Mathematically one may extend the idea of constant density down to lengths approaching zero, but physically once one reaches a length of the order of interparticle spacing, one sees single particles and their probabilistic collisions and it is not really clear what constant density at any instant is supposed to mean. Furthermore one may see a highly probabilistic system give rise to average values P, V, T and density in equilibrium consistent with a Newtonian smoothed over or average picture.

Thus we suggest that a particle moving with constant speed/momentum and described by a Newtonian $x(t)$ may have its deterministic motion break down at a certain length scale. In other words, x and t may no longer be linked and one may consider a probability of finding the particle at x within this length region. If Newtonian motion $x=vt$ ($v=\text{constant}$ for uniform motion) is replaced with another deterministic theory based on a different $x(t)$ such that on average $x=vt$, we argue this new deterministic motion would also break down at some length. Thus one is led to an unusual probabilistic view which decouples x and t .

Newtonian velocity, however, is based on two variables x and t , and if one has $P(x,p)$ for uniform motion, how does it describe direction and motion? Overall $P(x,p)$ being skewed in one direction or the other as a single real function is not consistent with the Newtonian average idea that all x points are the same for uniform motion. A solution is to utilize a vector probability $P(x,p)=\exp(ipx)$ which maps, for any x (i.e. even in regions smaller than the wavelength proportional to $1/p$) to density=1 i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. In such a case the spatial probabilities for motion to the left or right are not equal, nor do they need be. Thus a breakdown of deterministic motion has occurred with the introduction of the probability $\exp(ipx)$, but this stochastic motion still maps to a constant density for any x and so is consistent with Newtonian mechanics, while introducing new physics (interference) at scales of the order of \hbar/p .

We suggest that such an unusual situation is already found in the case of a photon which has an average E and p such that $E=pc$. One may use these smoothed over Newtonian like values to solve reflection/refraction problems, but the fluctuating nature of $\cos(-Et+px)$ which is part of the electric and magnetic fields and hence the energy and momentum densities through d/dt ($.5C_1 \text{ electric dot electric} + .5C_2 \text{ magnetic dot magnetic} + C_3 \text{ grad dot electric cross magnetic} = 0$ already shows a breakdown of smooth Newtonian variables E and p . Given the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ we suggest there is no reason that x , and t might also have this deterministic breakdown.

References

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